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INEQUALITY, POVERTY, AND UNDERDEVELOPMENT: THREATS TO EDUCATIONAL DEVELOPMENT, NATIONAL PEACE, AND SECURITY

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Abstract

Inequality is associated with poverty and poverty is amongst the indices of an underdeveloped society. These variables seem to be correlates of insecurity which can pose serious threats to education and national development as well as global peace in the 21st century. The issue of inequality, peace and underdevelopment has to do with socio-economic and psychological state of people and their environment. Once there is agitation in one's mind due to lack of some pressing or basic needs of life, there could be an outburst of anger even at the slightest provocation which eventually leads to serious violence. This paper hereby examines the diversity trend, and nature of inequality in Nigeria; poverty situation, causes of underdevelopment and their effects on educational development and national peace and security. It also evaluates the impact of some government policies that have been put forth over the years in an attempt to address these social menaces. The paper recommends in addition to others, that since global rule is amongst the major causes of inequality, poverty and underdevelopment, international communities should encourage democratic global governance where a developing country like Nigeria should be given right to participate in decision making process at both local and international levels on issues that affect her economy.

Keywords: Inequality, Poverty, Underdevelopment, Educational development, Peace, Security

Introduction

Inequality, poverty, and underdevelopment are serious social problems bedevilling the third world and developing countries of the world. The unequal distribution of power, prestige, wealth, and income are referred to as inequality. Naturally, there is unequal distribution of power, prestige, wealth, and income among individuals in every society. Inequalities are 'basically about relational disparities, denial of fair and equivalent enjoyment of rights, and the persistence of arbitrary discrepancies in the worth, status, dignity and freedoms of different people' (UNICEF & UN Women, 2013). Inequality can exist in a variety of different spheres such as income, wealth, education, health, and nutrition.

Interestingly, there are serious arguments amongst scholars regarding the nature of inequality. Scholars like Durkheim, (1947), Parson (1969), Weber (1958), argued that inequality especially in distribution of income is natural, appropriate, desirable, and hence inevitable. The basis of their arguments is that some people are naturally talented than others and have higher intelligent quotient, as such, should be allowed to hold

important functions in the society and paid higher as a way of compensation. However, scholar like Marx, (1868) argued that inequality or such unequal distribution of wealth is artificially created by unjust nature of class society like the capitalist system. According to him, inequality will vanish if capitalism collapses. Max (1868) further argued that this unequal distribution is what triggers tension, conflict, and class struggle that virtually ends in revolution which accounts for unrest and perplexity in the society. This is exemplified by what is happening in the Niger delta region of Nigeria.

On the other hand, poverty according to the United Nation (UN) statement, is a denial of choice, opportunities, a violation of human dignity, lack of basic capacity to participate effectively in society, not having enough to feed and clothe a family, not having quality school or clinic to go to, not having the land on which to grow one's food or a job to earn ones living. It means insecurity, powerlessness and exclusion of individual's households and communities; it means susceptibility to violence, and it often implies living on marginal or fragile environment, without access to clean water or sanitation.

The report from National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) (2020) revealed that about 40 percent of the total population, or almost 83 million people, live below the country's poverty line of 137,430 naira (\$381.75) per year. Poverty goes hand in hand with underdevelopment which results in backwardness generally.

Underdevelopment can also be explained in terms of relationship of exploitation of one country by another (Ashaver, 2013). According to him, all the countries classified as underdeveloped were exploited by others. He also noted that it is an established fact that development cannot take place where there is mass poverty and inequality. Nigeria, though naturally endowed with both material and human resources, is pathetically caught up in the web of underdevelopment, due to poverty and inequality. These have serious implications on peace and educational development in the country. The standard of education is low in terms of input and outcomes and only few people can afford quality education for their children. Due to inequality in the distribution of the resources, the aggrieved people who are in the poor populace become violent and the peace of the society is truncated. Its consequential effect on educational activities is evidenced in different parts of the country ranging from banditry, terrorism, kidnapping in Northern parts of the country to the agitations and militancy of the Niger Delta and Southeast regions of the country (Aina 2015). No peace or any serious educational development can strive in a poverty laden society orchestrated by inequality; hence the issue of inequality and poverty in the country should be given priority to avert their ill effect on national development especially on the educational sector which invariably is the driving force for any sustainable development.

Diversity, Nature and Trend of Income Inequality in Nigeria

According to Bakare (2012), there is very high disparity in the income distribution of the nation. That means, the income and the wealth of the nation seems to be unevenly distributed. We have some set of people who are very rich whose living standards are relatively high. Such people have access to the basic needs of life such as balanced diet, convenient shelter, basic infrastructure, good clothing, education etc. At the same time,

people who hold political offices or who are related to those that hold political offices.

World Bank (2008) in their analysis supported the issue of high disparity between the income of the richest 10 and 20 % and poorest 10 and 20% Nigeria population. According to Ucha (2010), in 2003, the income of the poorest 10 per cent of Nigeria's population was only 1.9% while that of the richest 10% was 33.2%. Anton (2011) stated that the existence of income inequality in Nigeria is deep, severe, and widespread. According to him, in 1994, the distribution of aggregate household income shows that the bottom 40% of the population receives only 15.7% of aggregate household income. On the other hand, the top 20% of Nigerian household received 42.9% of total household income. Perhaps even more striking, the top 5% of Nigerian families received 16% of aggregate household income, whereas the lowest 20% received only 4.7% of aggregate household income.

In addition to the above assertion, National Bureau of statistics (2010) in their statistics of consumption expenditure stated that out of the population of about 160 million people, 96 million Nigerians have just 20% purchasing power in the country. This group relates to those who strive from hand to mouth. They constitute the bottom line of the class structure and are exposed to various forms of degradation. What this means is that inequality is soaring high.

Oluwatayo (2008), noted an increase in income inequality disparity after the economic growth which Nigeria experienced between 1965-1975. According to him, the income inequality between the people in rural and urban areas in Nigeria is remarkably high, as those who live in rural area base all their income on agriculture which is today not a thriving sector in Nigeria. According to Aigbkan (2000), inequality in Nigeria as measured by the Gini coefficient, has been rising since 1985, except for slight decline in 1992. According to him it declined from 0.43 in 1985 to 0.41 in 1992 and rose to 0.49 in 1990. It remained unchanged at 0.488 between 2004 and even 2015 at the national level. However, at the sectoral and regional levels, in addition to there being variations among the national average, there seems to be a more marked increase in inequality between 1996 and 2004. Thus, the national average may have concealed rising inequality across states and sectors since the mid 1990's. The National Statistics survey result (2010) suggests rising income inequality in the country as measured by the Gini-coefficient. By this measure, income inequality rose from 0.429 in 2004 to 0.447 in 2010, indicating greater income inequality during the period.

State of Poverty in Nigeria

Poverty is best used to describe the state in which majority of Nigerian citizens find themselves. It is seen to be multidimensional, multifaceted with different manifestations. Anton (2011) quoting Webster third international dictionary, defined poverty as a state or conditions characterized, among other things by lack of material possession, existing without the luxuries and often the necessities of life. It can be described as a state of deprivation or lack of resources to meet basic needs (Economic Policy Watch, 2002). A UN75 (2020) report on "peace, dignity and equality on a healthy planet" sees poverty in a very clear perspective to include hunger and malnutrition, limited access to education and other basic services, social discrimination, and exclusion, as well as the lack of participation in decision-making. According to the report, more than 736 million people lived below the international poverty line in 2015. Around 10 per cent of the world population (pre-pandemic) was living in extreme poverty and struggling to fulfil the most basic needs like health, education, access to water and sanitation, to name a few. Nigeria as a nation is badly hit as revealed in the report of Mayah, Mariotti, Mere and Odo (2017) that 57 million Nigerians lack access to safe water, over 130 million are without access to adequate sanitation. Nigeria has the highest number of out of schoolchildren. World Bank (1990) distinguished between three classes of poverty namely: absolute, relative, and material poverty

Absolute poverty refers to the inability of the individual to provide himself with the basic needs such as food, clothing, shelter, portable water, health service, education, public transport etc. Nigerian Poverty Profile Report 2010 survey results revealed that 54.7% of Nigerians were living in poverty in 2004 but this increased to 60.9% (or 99,284,512 Nigerians) in 2010. Among the geo-political zones, the North-West and North-East recorded the highest rates at 70% and 69% respectively, while the South-West had the least at 49.8%. At the State level, Sokoto had the highest at 81.2% while Niger had the least at 33.8% during the reviewed period. This type of poverty leads to deprivation, non-participation in decision making affecting one's life.

Relative poverty recounts to the inability of certain section of the community or individuals to satisfy their basic needs. The 2010 profile report also shows that using this measure in 2004, Nigeria's relative poverty measurement stood at 54.4%, but increased to 69% (or 112,518,507 Nigerians) in 2010. The North-West and North-East geo-political zones recorded the highest poverty rates in the country with 77.7% and 76.3% respectively in 2010, while the South-West geo-political zone recorded the lowest at 59.1%. Among States, Sokoto, had the highest poverty rate at 86.4% while Niger had the lowest at 43.6% in the year under review.

Material poverty relates to lack of ownership and control of physical assets such as land and animal husbandry (UNDP, 1922). Poverty was also described in terms of the Dollar-per-day measure. The National Bureau of Statistics refers to the proportion of those living on less than US\$1 per day as materially poor. Applying this approach, according to the poverty line report, 51.6% of Nigerians were living below US\$1 per day in 2004, but this increased to 61.2% in 2010. The North-West geo-political zone recorded the highest percentage at 70.4%, while the South-West geo-political zone had the least at 50.1%. Sokoto had the highest rate among States at 81.9%, while Niger had

the least at 33.9%. According to the Nigerian Living Standards Survey (NLSS) report as cited in Adesoji (2020) released by the NBS covering the year 2019, 40.1% of Nigerians are classified as poor by national standards. Further details provided in the nation-wide survey report show that Northern states in Nigeria rank poorest. According to the report, 9 of top 10 poorest states in Nigeria are from the northern region with Sokoto, Taraba and Jigawa being the poorest. The summary report also shows that 52.1% of rural dwellers in Nigeria are poor, while only 18.04% of urban dwellers are classified as poor. According to NBS, on average, 4 out of 10 individuals in Nigeria has real per capita expenditures below N137,430 per year, which translates to N376.5 per day.

All the above threatening figures put together, seem to establish the unavoidable picture of a country that presents such paradox of being both a large oil exporter and amongst the poorest nations at the same time. The manifestations of poverty in the country make it a serious social problem because it affects the peace and security of the larger society, educational development inclusive. From the statistics presented by the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) for 2020, 40% or over 80 million Nigerians live in abject poverty. Though the figure for 2021 is yet to be released, the estimates show a grim state indeed. The number of poor Nigerians is quite high. No wonder, the surge in insecurity, banditry, kidnapping, terrorism, climate change and other distasteful consequences (NBS 2020).

Under-development in Nigeria

Nigeria is naturally endowed with natural and human resources yet underdeveloped despite this natural advantage. Looking at the different dimensions or criteria used to classify a nation as underdeveloped, one can conclusively classify Nigeria as an underdeveloped nation. For example, when you take underdevelopment as a means of comparing levels of development, Nigeria's level of development in so many ramifications cannot be compared to that of the first and second world countries like US, UK etc in terms of infrastructural development, technological advancement, educational development, social services, information technology, transportation, standard and safe health services etc. This makes the nation to depend on the developed countries for importation of most goods and services for standard and healthy living.

Human social development is uneven; from economic point of view, some parts of the country have advanced further by producing more and becoming wealthier e.g., the urban areas while most of the places are undeveloped especially rural areas. Most of the host communities where the mineral resources are mined from are highly backward, or undeveloped, impoverished and that is why the youths of these host communities engage in social unrest and all kinds of vices to draw the attention of the leaders because they feel marginalized, exploited, impoverished and government policies do not favour them.

Theoretical Framework

The Dependency Theory: The dependency school would be used as the theoretical framework to buttress the effects of the colonial legacy on the development of Nigeria. The concept of dependency was first used by Latin American writers seeking to account

for the fact that, despite having won formal independence from Spain or Portugal before the middle of the 19th century, a hundred years later, their countries had mostly failed to develop into modern, industrialized societies. In the 1950s it became the basis of influential analyses of development by scholars such as Furtado, Dos Santos, and Fernando Cardoso. Other terms used to bear the same meaning with dependency include semi-colonialism which Lenin used in 1916 with reference to Latin America. Nkrumah, and Fanon called it Neo-colonialism, referring to post independence Africa in the 1960s while Gunder Frank, studying the Latin American experience from the early 19th to the 1960s called it "Underdevelopment".

According to Gunder Frank, his dependency or underdevelopment thesis holds that the development of the west was possible through the subordination and exploitation of the former colonies at the expense of the periphery's stagnation and impoverishment which has continued to be so. Real economic development at the periphery only occurred during world wars I and II or during the depression of the 1930s when trade and investment links between the metropole and the periphery were broken or weakened. The solution to the problem of underdevelopment was therefore to end the condition of dependency through a revolutionary break. This has also been referred to as "delinking", or "new international economic order". Their economic structures tend to reflect the original reason for making them colonies: the production of primary commodities for export, and the creation of infrastructures such as railways, roads, ports, and telecommunications oriented to exports, not the promotion of an integrated national economy offering viable internal markets for more than basic goods. In the most extreme cases, the whole economy may be based on the export of just one or two commodities and be vulnerable to world market fluctuation or bad weather.

Explaining the concept of underdevelopment, Saul (2006) stated that the underdeveloped nations produce what they don't consume and consume what they don't produce. This underwrites significantly to increasing indebtedness which obliged so many of them to consent to the "structural adjustment" programmes imposed by IMF and World Bank as a condition for further aid. Ashaver (2013) perceived structural adjustment as a new form of dependency and reliance on a few commodity exports which were at the root of their economic difficulties. This theory explains the exact experience and condition of Nigeria. Till date, Nigeria as a nation is still depending on the western countries for survival in so many areas. Most of the goods used in the country are manufactured and imported from the west at the exchange of our crude oil which is the only export product we have as a nation seconded by few other agricultural products.

Structural/Economic Theory of Poverty by Rainwater Lee

Rainwater Lee believes that the structure of the economy determines the level of poverty. The economic structure includes different employment level and the nature of the distribution of income. Thus, an individual is poor not because he is not hard working but does not have the opportunity to work. He is made poor as a result of the economic system that denied him his share of the income and inequitable distribution of income. (Jordan, 2004 as cited by Ogbeide and Agu 2015). Its relevance is applicable in

this research as seen in a typical Nigerian situation of teeming unemployment worsened by retrenchment and laying of workers due to economic meltdown.

Facilitators of Inequality, Poverty, and Underdevelopment in Nigeria

The major facilitators of poverty, inequality and underdevelopment in Nigeria are global rules and state policies. The origin of global rule predates the colonial period (Ashaver, 2013). The rules according to Ashaver, is born out of selfish interest of the developed countries who keeps their colonies under subordination even after independence through globalization to the disadvantage of their own economic development. Globalization is characterised by liberalization and intensification of international linkages in trade, finance, market, politics, and culture accelerated microelectronics and information technology. There is therefore the accelerated integration of capital production and markets globally, a process driven by the logic of corporate profitability. The process of globalization and liberalization of trade and market rather than enhancing development, reduction of poverty and inequality has led to the enslavement of the nation by the capitalist west. Global rules and domestic policies tend to enhance poverty in Nigeria. Some "big" countries of the world through the new international financial structure have imposed on the rest of the world including Nigeria their own rules that determine how local policies of developing countries are to be formulated and implemented. This new structure is not development friendly at all. Rather it is project of consolidation of inequality between nations and between classes within nations (Soederbeg, 2004).

Part of the effect of globalization is high indebtedness which made Nigeria to accept though against the advice of the political bureau of that time, the IMF and World Bank induced structural adjustment with stringent conditionalities of devaluation of currency, removal of subsidy, retrenchment of workers, high exchange rate and inflation in the country which has also inflicted poverty and inequality in the country. It has been noted that the hardships Nigerians are now facing are caused by the effects of SAP. The IMF policy that led to decline in trade swung Nigeria into perpetual indebtedness. Bad state policies and their implementations also contribute to poverty, inequality, and underdevelopment. The state policies also reinforce the global rules and that makes it like a vicious cycle. The policies of the nation encourage or permits state government to collect loans from foreign firms or World Bank. Many state governments are highly indebted and ironically such monies are not used for development purposes but eventually end in the hands of the politicians with little or no impact on the lives of the citizens. Income inequality and poverty may also be caused by a number of interrelated factors, such as, level of education and training, occupation, some other professions, regional, ethnic, and even political differences (Umez, 2000).

Poverty and inequality are also fuelled by corruption, misappropriation and mismanagement of funds from the nations' resources which has resulted in high rate of unemployment especially among the youths. High unemployment rates render personal income even more divergent. This is one of the major factors contributing to poverty in Nigeria. Ucha, (2010) noted strong correlation between unemployment and poverty. Ucha posited that when people are unemployed, their source of livelihood depletes over

time; the cost of living becomes high, and the standard of living goes down. Many people in Nigeria lack the opportunity of being employed. The formal unemployment rate in Nigeria as estimated to be 23.9% in 2011 from 21.1% in 2010 and Nigeria ranked 61st across the world countries with high unemployment rate. (CIA Facebook). Unemployment induced poverty increases the crime rate and violence in the country. Most unemployed youths resort to crimes such as armed robbery, kidnapping for ransom, internet fraud and other forms of fraudulent activities. The ugly incident of 15th March 2014 where over 6.5 million Nigerians went out to secure jobs meant for 4000 positions in the Nigerian Immigration service's paint the grim situation of the state of unemployment among the youths in Nigeria.

Over concentration on oil revenue and neglecting of other sectors like agriculture and solid minerals which employs virtually all the rural population is also an issue of concern. The oil revenue is poorly distributed among the population, with higher government spending in urban areas than rural areas. Again, the process of oil extraction has resulted in significant pollution, which further harms the agricultural sector.

Other factors that cause inequality, poverty and underdevelopment are corruption at all levels, poor attitude to work, laziness, tribalism, wrong policies, bad leaders, non-diversification of the economy, poor educational system, insecurity, political instability, and ethnic conflict. The truth is that there has not been explicit concern about poverty, inequality, and underdevelopment on government policies; all that are being done now is shadow of events.

Effects of Poverty, Inequality and Under-development on the Society

There are several effects and deficiencies associated with poverty, inequality, and underdevelopment in Nigeria. Poverty situation in Nigeria has made the window of opportunity to remain closed to the poor masses. (Ucha 2010). Inequality has given rise to class society while underdevelopment has made the masses practically inactive. All these have impacted negatively on the educational development, peace, and security of the country. The lack of financial empowerments limits the choices of the masses in almost everything.

Educational development is affected because it takes money to run the sector. Schools lack the basic infrastructures and facilities to function properly. In the country today, public schools are not "working" / delivering the expected outcomes hence the incessant strike actions by teachers at all levels. The poverty situation has caused severe hardship to the citizenry to the extent that most parents cannot comfortably sponsor their children in good schools.

The state of the public schools has led to the upsurge of privately owned schools with better facilities and infrastructures. Due to the uneven distribution of resources / power, the few who are controlling the resources send their children to private schools. The children of the poor masses who cannot afford the fees paid in the privately owned schools are exposed to harsh and unconducive learning environment. The hardship caused by poverty, unequal distribution of resources, and underdevelopment breeds constant social tensions that has promoted aggression among the youths who believe that they have been short-changed by the Nigerian system. (Ajah, 2019). The frequent display

of aggressive behaviours among students threatens the overall wellbeing and safety of the school environment, larger society, and the attainment of the national educational goal.

Poverty and inequality according to Ford (2007) has also been linked up to high crime rates as reflected in the banditry, terrorism, kidnapping and killings in different parts of the country as well as the agitations in the Niger Delta region where there is a sharp contrast between the rich and the poor. The masses cause social unrest because wealth gotten from their territory does not get to them. In fact, poverty, inequality, and underdevelopment situation in Nigeria is a pitiable condition that needs serious attention.

Conclusion

Convincing statistical evidences as presented in this paper, have proved that Nigeria is bedevilled with high level of poverty, inequality, and underdevelopment. Furthermore, Nigeria as a nation, has many good policies that are meant to impart positively on national development, but implementations have been hindered by state capture and bad global rules which are weighed against third world countries especially Africa. The conclusion therefore is that the aforementioned menaces are inimical to educational development, peace, and security of the Nigerian nation. A more concerted effort is therefore needed from all and sundry especially from the government and policy makers to combat the menace of inequality, poverty, and underdevelopment in the country.

The Way Forward

In order to combat the problem of poverty, inequality, and underdevelopment, the following measures should be considered:

1. There should be an immediate policy effort to fine-tune the economy in the direction of a reduced poverty and inequality levels that will generate sufficient growth to revamp and bolster the economy.
2. Secondly, the link between economic and political power must be re-evaluated for progress to be made.
3. There should be end to the condition of dependency through a revolutionary break.
4. Again, since the majority of the poor in the country dwell in the rural areas, there is need to focus development efforts on the rural regions, i.e. government should seek to develop all sectors of rural economy and link them up effectively.
5. There should be infrastructural development, provision of social services, employment and income generating opportunities to the rural dwellers in general and the poor in particular.
6. The conditions for pro-poor growth include reducing the disparity in access to human and physical capital, reducing disparities in access to financial credit. The government reforms should focus on building human capital by refocusing on human development, redesigning programmes to discourage corrupt practices.
7. There should be improved governance to reduce 'state capture' by the rich and leakages in poverty alleviation programmes.
8. Invest in basic and technical education to raise the supply of skilled labour and create job opportunities for the masses to be gainfully engaged.

9. Agricultural sector should be improved. There should also be consistency, rather than reversal, in policies.

In addition to the above points, Aigbokham (2000) noted the following steps that should be followed if third world countries are to develop and reduce poverty and inequality:

1. Developing countries should have more rights of participation in decision making processes in the IMF, World Bank and WHO, which should also be made more accountable to the public and to the local and poor communities. This will enhance appropriate and democratic global governance.
2. Governance at the national level should combine economic development, environmental concern, and social justice.
3. Urgent measures are needed to address the youth unemployment crisis
4. Creation of employment opportunities should not be left for the government and its agencies alone, but private sectors are encouraged to venture into entrepreneurship development. Remuneration of workers should be reviewed upwardly to meet with the current central bank inflation index.
5. States should evolve policies that are development oriented. This calls for provision of good roads, portable and safe water, education, social

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